

Tagungsnummer

P5

Thema

Kommission I: Bodenphysik und Bodenhydrologie

Wasser-, Stoff- und Energietransport im Boden und zum Grundwasser

Autoren

M. Poltoradnev¹, J. Ingwersen¹, T. Streck¹

¹Universität Hohenheim, Biogeophysik, Stuttgart

Titel

Spatial and temporal variability of soil water content in two regions of Southwest German

Abstract

Soil water content (SWC) plays a key role in partitioning of energy and water fluxes on the land surface. Knowledge about spatial and temporal variability of topsoil water content is crucial for understanding land surface processes, improving climate and hydrology modeling. In recent study, we investigated SWC variability, its relation to the mean spatial soil water content (q_m